

Coronary Flow Regulation and it's signaling by adenosine.

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Abstract:

Adenosine acts through its receptors (A1, A2A, A2B, and A3) via G-proteins and causes an increase in coronary flow (CF) mostly through A2A AR. However, the role of other ARs in the modulation of CF is not well understood. Using knockouts (KO), we investigated the role for each AR in the regulation of CF. Using the isolated heart from A3 KO mice; we reported an increase in A2A-mediated CF. Similarly, we found an increase in CF in A1 KO mice with A2A agonist (CGS-21680; CGS). In addition, in A2A KO mice response to CGS was abolished, thus confirming the KO. On the other hand, A2A KO mice showed a decrease in CF to NECA (non-selective agonist). BAY60-6583 (A2B selective agonist; BAY) was without an effect on CF in A2B KO mice; however, it increased CF significantly in A2A KO. CGS also caused a significant increase in CF in A2B KO mice. In addition, exogenous adenosine-induced increase in CF in wild type, A2A KO, and A2B KO mice were significantly reduced with catalase. BAY-induced increase in CF in WT was significantly inhibited with glibenclamide. Overall, our data support stimulatory roles for A2A and A2B and inhibitory roles for A1 and A3 in the regulation of CF. These observations provide new evidence for the presence of all four ARs in CF regulation. We propose, that activation of A2A/B may release H₂O₂ which then activates KATP channels, leading to vasodilation. These studies may lead to better understanding of the role of ARs in coronary disease and better therapeutic approaches.

Biography:

S Jamal Mustafa is the Professor of Physiology and Pharmacology at West Virginia University (WVU). He has received Dean's Award for Excellence in Research from SOM in 2008 and became a Robert C. Byrd Professor in 2010 and received Chancellor's Award for Outstanding Achievement in Research and Scholarly Activities from HSC, in 2013. He has also published over 200 manuscripts. His past work has led to the approval of an A2A selective AR agonist (Lexican®) for myocardial perfusion imaging. Currently, he is using AR and β adrenergic receptor KOs to better understand the relationship between these receptors in coronary flow regulation.

Carcinoid heart disease in patients with neuroendocrine tumors: Prevalence and predisposing factors

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Abstract:

Background: By releasing vasoactive substances into the circulation, neuroendocrine tumors can cause right-sided valvular heart disease. Factors associated with the development of carcinoid heart disease (CHD) are poorly understood. The incidence is reported to be as high as 50%.

Methods: Our sample from 2012 and 2013 included all consecutive patients with neuroendocrine tumors referred to our institution undergoing echocardiographic studies.

Results: Among 532 patients treated in our center during the study period (54% male, mean age 62 years, mean duration from diagnosis to baseline echo: 63 months) 63 patients (11.8%) were found to have CHD. 43/63 (68%) had CHD already at baseline of whom 13 had to be referred to surgery for valve replacement after baseline echo, and 20/63 (31%) developed CHD during follow-up. Patients with CHD were more likely to have episodic flushing (38% vs 22%; $p=0.006$), the primary tumor located in the ileum (62% vs 34%; $p=0.004$) with frequent liver and peritoneal/soft tissue metastases. Serotonin was elevated in all CHD patients (100% vs 40%; $p<0.001$). Progressive disease according to the RESCIST criteria was more prevalent among CHD patients (60% vs 41%; $p=0.004$). CHD patients received more frequently somatostatin analogs (52% vs 40%; $p=0.04$) and underwent more frequently hepatic artery embolization (24% vs 14%; $p=0.04$). Echocardiographic follow-up (mean 38 months) was available for 469 (88%) of the patients and demonstrated dilated chambers of the right heart (right atrium 39 vs 35 mm; right ventricle 36 vs 32 mm), and higher RV pressure (32 vs 26 mmHg; $p<0.0001$ for all). A total of 21/63 (33%) CHD patients had to be referred to cardiac surgery (13/21 [62%] for isolated tricuspid valve replacement (TVR), 8/21 [38%] for TVR+pulmonary valve replacement). There were no patients with involvement of the mitral- or aortic valve, the prevalence of intracardiac metastases was 5.6%. All-cause mortality (28.6% vs 15.4%; $p=0.01$) and mean survival (101 vs 128 months; $p=0.03$) was significantly different between in CHD and non-CHD patients.

Conclusions: The prevalence of CHD in our series was significantly lower than previously reported. Somatostatin analogs and hepatic dearterialization did not prevent development of CHD. All-cause mortality and mean survival was significantly reduced in CHD patients.

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Biography:

Marc-Alexander Ohlow, MD, PhD is a Professor of Internal Medicine at Philipps-University Marburg and vice-director of the cardiology department at Zentralklinik Bad Berka. Dr. Ohlow did his PhD work about congenital left ventricular aneurysms and diverticula in adult populations. His present research areas include interventional cardiology, structural heart disease, heart rhythm device implantation, and inflammatory cardiomyopathy. He authored >80 peer-reviewed papers in the field of cardiac disease, and serves on the Editorial Board of the Journal of Geriatric Cardiology.

Early discharge after cardiac implantable electronic device implantations: Is this the future?

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Abstract:

Background: In order to decrease the ever-increasing healthcare costs, strategies to reduce hospital length of stay and costs would be important. We analyzed patients after cardiac implantable electronic device (CIED) implantation to assess timing of complications and thereby evaluate whether it is safe to discharge patients home early (the same day or after <24 hours) post-implantation.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective cohort analysis of all patients undergoing new CIED implantation or device upgrade at our institution from Jan 2008 to Dec 2014. We evaluated the patient demographics, comorbidities, and timing of complications post CIED implantation. Timing of complications was divided into intra-operative, 0-6 hours (h), >6-24 h, and >24 h post implant. One-year post-implant follow-up (FU) was performed in our CIED-clinic.

Results: A total of 1,868 patients (68% men, average age 70 years, 85% hypertension, 39% diabetes, 57% coronary artery disease, and average LVEF 41%) received 703 (38%) pacemaker, 448 (24%) implantable cardioverter defibrillator (ICD), and 639 (34%) cardiac resynchronization therapy (CRT) devices. A total of 199 (11%) patients experienced 214 complications during FU. Most complications (75%) occurred >24 hours post implantation (median 7 days post implantation) (Table 1). In univariate analysis, patients with complications following CIED implantation had significantly lower LVEF, more frequently anticoagulation/antiplatelet therapy, and received more frequently ICD (especially CRT-D) devices ($p < 0.05$ for all).

Conclusions: Most post-CIED implant complications occur >24 h after implantation. Therefore, it is not advisable to discharge patients undergoing new device implantation or upgrade procedures at the same day or after less than 24 h, unless potent ambulatory monitoring for complications is available.

Table 1: Timing of complications after CIED implantation

Type of complication	Complication and timing				Incidence
	Intra-procedure	0-6 hours	>6-24 hours	> 24 hours	
Pericardial effusion/ Tamponade	0	2	2	5	9 (0.5%)
Pneumothorax	1	6	21	12	40 (2.1%)
Hemothorax	0	0	3	1	4 (0.4%)
Lead dislodgement	0	2	12	87	101 (5.4%)
Hematoma needing evacuation	0	0	3	30	33 (1.8%)
Pocket infection	0	0	0	23	23 (4.2%)
Other	1	1	0	2	4 (0.4%)
Total	2 (0.9%)	11 (5.1%)	41 (19.2%)	160 (74.8%)	

Biography:

Marc-Alexander Ohlow, MD, PhD is a Professor of Internal Medicine at Philipps-University Marburg and vice-director of the cardiology department at Zentralklinik Bad Berka. Dr. Ohlow did his PhD work about congenital left ventricular aneurysms and diverticula in adult populations. His present research areas include interventional cardiology, structural heart disease, heart rhythm device implantation, and inflammatory cardiomyopathy. He authored >80 peer-reviewed papers in the field of cardiac disease, and serves on the Editorial Board of the Journal of Geriatric Cardiology.